

1 IDE Algorithm for Bimetallic Cluster Structure Optimization

Algorithm 1 Population Evolution

Require: Population \mathbf{P} , strategy type s

Ensure: Evolved population \mathbf{P}

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1: for each individual  $\mathbf{X}_i \in \mathbf{P}$  do
2:   Mutation:
3:   if  $s = \text{"explorer"}$  then
4:      $\mathbf{V}_i \leftarrow \mathbf{X}_{r1} + F \times (\mathbf{X}_{r2} - \mathbf{X}_{r3})$ 
5:   else if  $s = \text{"developer"}$  then
6:      $\mathbf{V}_i \leftarrow \mathbf{B}_P + F \times (\mathbf{X}_{r1} - \mathbf{X}_{r2})$ 
7:   else
8:      $\mathbf{V}_i \leftarrow \mathbf{X}_i + K \times (\mathbf{B}_P - \mathbf{X}_i) + F \times (\mathbf{X}_{r1} - \mathbf{X}_{r2}) + F \times (\mathbf{X}_{r3} - \mathbf{X}_i)$ 
9:   end if
10:
11:   Crossover:
12:    $j_{rand} \leftarrow \text{randint}(1, D)$  {Ensure at least one dimension changes}
13:   for  $j = 1$  to  $D$  do
14:     if  $(\text{rand}() < CR)$  OR  $(j = j_{rand})$  then
15:        $U_i^j \leftarrow V_i^j$  {Take from mutant vector}
16:     else
17:        $U_i^j \leftarrow X_i^j$  {Take from target vector}
18:     end if
19:   end for
20:
21:   Selection:
22:    $E(U_i) \leftarrow \text{L-BFGS}(U_i)$  {Local optimization is key}
23:   if  $E(U_i) < E(\mathbf{X}_i)$  then
24:      $\mathbf{X}_i \leftarrow U_i$ 
25:     if  $E(U_i) < E(\mathbf{B}_P)$  then
26:        $\mathbf{B}_P \leftarrow U_i$ 
27:     end if
28:   end if
29: end for
30:
31: return  $\mathbf{P}$ 
```

Algorithm 2 Atom Swap Operation

Require: Individual \mathbf{X} **Ensure:** Updated individual \mathbf{X}

- 1: **if** ($N_{pt} \neq 0$) AND ($N_{pt} \neq N$) **then**
- 2: Randomly select a Pt atom a (index 0 to $N_{pt} - 1$)
- 3: Randomly select a Ni atom b (index N_{pt} to $N - 1$)
- 4: Store \mathbf{x}_a in temporary variable
- 5: Set $\mathbf{x}_a \leftarrow \mathbf{x}_b$
- 6: Set $\mathbf{x}_b \leftarrow$ stored value
- 7: $E_{new} \leftarrow$ L-BFGS(\mathbf{X}) {Re-optimize after swap}
- 8: **if** $E_{new} \geq E(\mathbf{X})$ **then**
- 9: Store \mathbf{x}_a in temporary variable
- 10: Set $\mathbf{x}_a \leftarrow \mathbf{x}_b$
- 11: Set $\mathbf{x}_b \leftarrow$ stored value {Revert positions}
- 12: **end if**
- 13: **end if**
- 14:
- 15: **return** \mathbf{X}

Algorithm 3 Exchange Best Individuals

Require: Three populations $\mathbf{P}_e, \mathbf{P}_d, \mathbf{P}_b$ **Ensure:** Updated populations $\mathbf{P}_e, \mathbf{P}_d, \mathbf{P}_b$

- 1: **for** $i = 1$ to 3 **do**
- 2: $\mathbf{P}_s \leftarrow$ population i
- 3: $\mathbf{P}_t \leftarrow$ population $(i \bmod 3) + 1$
- 4: **if** $E(\mathbf{B}_{\mathbf{P}_s}) < E(\mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{P}_t})$ **then**
- 5: Replace $\mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{P}_t}$ in \mathbf{P}_t with $\mathbf{B}_{\mathbf{P}_s}$
- 6: Update $\mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{P}_t}$ for \mathbf{P}_t
- 7: **end if**
- 8: **end for**
- 9:
- 10: **return** $\mathbf{P}_e, \mathbf{P}_d, \mathbf{P}_b$

Algorithm 4 Main Framework of Improved DE

Require: Total atoms N , Pt atoms N_{pt} , max iterations $T = 200$, exchange interval S

Ensure: Global best structure \mathbf{G}

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1: Initialize parameters:
2:  $N_p \leftarrow \lfloor (N + 5)/5 \rfloor \times 5$ 
3: Initialize three populations:  $\mathbf{P}_e$  (Explorer),  $\mathbf{P}_d$  (Developer),  $\mathbf{P}_b$  (Balancer)
4:  $p_s \leftarrow 0.5$ ,  $c \leftarrow 0$ 
5: Initialize populations:
6: for each population  $\mathbf{P} \in \{\mathbf{P}_e, \mathbf{P}_d, \mathbf{P}_b\}$  do
7:   for  $j = 1$  to  $N_p$  do
8:     if historical best structure exists then
9:        $\mathbf{X}_j \leftarrow$  load and modify historical structure
10:    else
11:       $\mathbf{X}_j \leftarrow$  generate random structure within radius  $r_0 \cdot N^{1/3}$ 
12:    end if
13:     $E(\mathbf{X}_j) \leftarrow$  L-BFGS( $\mathbf{X}_j$ ) {Local optimization}
14:  end for
15:   $\mathbf{B}_\mathbf{P} \leftarrow \arg \min_{\mathbf{X} \in \mathbf{P}} E(\mathbf{X})$ 
16: end for
17:  $\mathbf{G} \leftarrow \arg \min\{\mathbf{B}_{\mathbf{P}_e}, \mathbf{B}_{\mathbf{P}_d}, \mathbf{B}_{\mathbf{P}_b}\}$ 
18: Main Loop:
19: for  $t = 1$  to  $T$  do
20:    $E_{prev} \leftarrow E(\mathbf{G})$ 
21:   {Evolve populations in parallel}
22:    $\mathbf{P}_e \leftarrow$  Evolve( $\mathbf{P}_e$ , “explorer”)
23:    $\mathbf{P}_d \leftarrow$  Evolve( $\mathbf{P}_d$ , “developer”)
24:    $\mathbf{P}_b \leftarrow$  Evolve( $\mathbf{P}_b$ , “balancer”)
25:   {Atom swap operation}
26:   for each population  $\mathbf{P} \in \{\mathbf{P}_e, \mathbf{P}_d, \mathbf{P}_b\}$  do
27:     for each individual  $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbf{P}$  do
28:       if  $\text{rand}() < p_s$  then
29:          $\mathbf{X} \leftarrow$  Swap( $\mathbf{X}$ )
30:       end if
31:     end for
32:   end for
33:   Update  $\mathbf{B}_\mathbf{P}$  for each population and  $\mathbf{G}$ 
34:   {Inter-population information exchange}
35:   if  $t \bmod S = 0$  then
36:     Exchange( $\mathbf{P}_e, \mathbf{P}_d, \mathbf{P}_b$ )
37:   end if
38:   {Dynamically adjust probability}
39:   if  $E(\mathbf{G}) < E_{prev}$  then
40:      $c \leftarrow 0$ ,  $p_s \leftarrow 0.2$ 
41:   else
42:      $c \leftarrow c + 1$ ,  $p_s \leftarrow \min(0.8, 0.2 + 0.01 \times c)$ 
43:   end if
44: end for
45: return  $\mathbf{G}$ 
```
